

Frameworks and platforms

F1-Guava: It is an open source library set (created by Google). Facilitates best coding practices and helps reduce coding errors. In addition, it provides useful methods for collections, caching, concurrency, common annotations, string processing, API gateways construction, among others.

Main functionalities:

- 1) Creation of new types of collections, such as Multimap and Multiset
- 2) Programming for concurrency
- 3) Programming of API gateways

Website: <https://github.com/google/guava>

F2-Netflix Eureka: Eureka is a REST service, mainly used in the AWS cloud, to which it is closely linked. Eureka behaves as a server, whose objective is to register and locate existing microservices, report their location, their status and relevant data on each of them. In addition, it facilitates load balanced and fault tolerance.

Main functionalities:

- 1) Microservices registration
- 2) Discover microservices
- 3) Load balancer

Website: <https://github.com/Netflix/eureka/wiki/Eureka-at-a-glance>

F3-Netflix Zuul: Zuul is a proxy inverse or *edge service* that allows both routing and filtering requests dynamically, as well as monitoring and securing them. This component acts as an entry point to the microservices, that is, it is responsible for requesting an instance of a specific microservice from Eureka and its routing towards the service that we want to consume.

Main functionalities:

- 1) Secure, balance and route requests to microservices
- 2) It has several filters focused on managing different requests
- 3) It can act as an API gateway

Website: <https://github.com/Netflix/zuul>

F4-Netflix Hystrix: It is a library offered by Netflix designed to isolate access points to remote systems, services and third-party libraries, stopping cascading failures and improving resilience in complex distributed systems where the probability of failure is inevitable.

Main functionalities:

- 1) Execution of calls to external or internal systems in the background
- 2) Possibility of establishing semaphores (thread pools), for each request
- 3) Provides methods to manage the propagation of errors in cascade

Website: <https://github.com/Netflix/Hystrix>

F5-RabbitMQ: RabbitMQ is a message queuing tool called a messaging broker or queue manager. Simply put, it is software where queues can be defined, applications can connect to such queues and transfer/read messages on them.

Main functionalities:

- 1) Flexible routing
- 2) Fault tolerance
- 3) Guarantee the delivery and order of messages

Website: <https://www.rabbitmq.com>

F6-Kubernetes: Kubernetes is a portable and extensible open source platform to manage workloads and services. Kubernetes makes automation and declarative setup easy. It has

a large and rapidly growing ecosystem. The support, tools and services for Kubernetes are widely available.

Main functionalities:

- 1) Container platform
- 2) Container orchestrator
- 3) Workload management

Website: <https://kubernetes.io/en/docs/concepts/overview/what-is-kubernetes/>

F7-Netflix Turbine: Is a tool for aggregating streams of Server-Sent Event (SSE) JSON data into a single stream. The targeted use case is metrics streams from instances in an SOA being aggregated for dashboards.

Main functionalities:

- 1) Monitoring clusters
- 2) List active servers in the system
- 3) Discover services

Website: <https://github.com/Netflix/Turbine>

F8-Swagger: It is a framework to document Rest APIs. Additionally, it is possible to describe, produce, consume, and display APIs.

Main functionalities:

- 1) Authentication with OAuth from the swagger interface
- 2) Describe the functionality of the endpoint
- 3) Provide APIs for microservices

Website: <https://swagger.io>

F9-Redis: It is a data structure store of values of fast and open source memory key. Redis incorporates a set of versatile in-memory data structures that allow you to easily create a variety of custom applications

Main functionalities:

- 1) Caching
- 2) Session Management
- 3) In-memory data structure

Website: <https://aws.amazon.com/en/ElastiCache/what-is-redis/>

F10-Apache Zookeeper: provides a centralized service for various tasks such as for maintenance configuration example, or distributed synchronization services group. Such services are normally consumed by other distributed applications.

Main functionalities:

- 1) Provide configuration management
- 2) Allow replicas on multiple hosts
- 3) Allow coordination between distributed processes

Website: <https://zookeeper.apache.org>

F11-Netflix Archaius: It is a configuration management library. Simply put, it is a framework that can be used to collect configuration properties from many different sources, offering fast and secure access for threads. In addition to this, the library allows properties to change dynamically at runtime, making it possible for the system to obtain these variations without having to restart the application.

Main functionalities:

- 1) Offers dynamic properties
- 2) *Callback* mechanisms
- 3) Offers ready-to-use implementations of dynamic configuration sources such as URL, JDBC and some databases, such as Amazon DynamoDB

Website: <https://github.com/Netflix/archaius/wiki>

F12-Netflix Ribbon: Is a library used for process intercommunication, which incorporates load balancing.

Main functionalities:

- 1) Provide load balancers
- 2) Fault tolerance
- 3) Support of multiple protocols (HTTP, TCP, UDP) in an asynchronous and reactive model

Website: <https://github.com/Netflix/ribbon>